

**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
Challenges in Higher Education**
Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

Prototype Teaching Methods, Tools and Materials

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GEDIS

Gender Diversity in Information Science:

Challenges in Higher Education

Prototype Teaching Methods, Tools and Materials

Barcelona, 30/11/2025

UNIVERSITAT DE
BARCELONA

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1. Introduction

This result consists of a curated set of prototype teaching methods, tools and learning materials developed by the partners and, in several cases, co-created with students in the GEDIS Summer School under staff supervision. These prototypes directly address the gaps in gender inclusivity identified in the curriculum analysis and expert consultations. The collection includes open-access resources such as lesson plans, classroom activities, assessment tasks, multilingual open educational resources (OER) and examples of game-based learning, all explicitly embedding gender perspectives into core information science topics. The materials are fully documented, ready to be piloted within LIS programmes across the partner institutions, and will form the basis of the professors' toolkit to be finalised and openly released under WP6.

To achieve this result, the consortium developed and tested prototype teaching methods, tools and materials that respond directly to the gaps in gender inclusivity identified in the Comprehensive Curriculum Analysis Report and the Consensus Document on Innovative Teaching Strategies. Partners co-designed learning activities, lesson outlines and assessment tasks that embed gender perspectives into core information science topics such as information literacy, user experience, open data, translation, hate speech and mis- and disinformation, algorithmic bias, and women in science and engineering.

These prototypes were implemented and refined through GEDIS staff training activities and the Summer School in Barcelona, where undergraduate students from all partner institutions worked with multilingual OER, serious game sessions and group projects explicitly addressing gender issues in information science. Feedback from students and lecturers was collected to assess relevance, clarity and

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transferability, and was used to improve the structure and guidance accompanying the materials.

As a result, WP2 now offers a coherent, adaptable collection of prototype teaching methods (such as game-based learning scenarios, collaborative analysis of gendered data sets and guided curriculum-redesign exercises), tools (including a curriculum analysis rubric, checklists for gender-inclusive course design and a serious print-and-play game) and open-access teaching materials (multilingual OER, lesson plans and activity sheets). These resources enhance the inclusivity and relevance of LIS education by providing educators with practical, adaptable instruments that can be integrated into existing courses or used to design new gender-sensitive learning units.

2. Prototypes designed by teaching staff and summer school students

2.1 Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy

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Paradoksi medijske i informacijske pismenosti

Paradoks normativnosti:
Pismenost nije univerzalna - živi unutar konteksta.
Kako povezati demokratiju, kulturu participacije i pismenost?

Paradoks odgovornosti:
Prijenos odgovornosti s institucija na pojedince.
Može li pojedinac izdržati SVE odgovornosti današnjice?

Vremenski paradoks:
Kako podučavati i predviđati tehnologije budućnosti?
Historijski kontekst sredstava i navika informisanja.

Paradoks povjerenja:
Da li svi žele biti racionalni i informisani?
Kako graditi povjerenje podučavanjem sumnje?

Paradoks neutralnosti:
Inherentna političnost informacije i znanja.
Medijska i informacijska pismenost nije neutralna u represivnim društvima.

LITERATURA
Hajrija Osmanhodžić, Luka Bošković, Lejla Mulabećirović. Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy: The Crisis of Information. Milton Park, Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, 2022.

Povezanost sa projektom GEDIS
Ovaj resurs je dio samopisnog projekta GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), koji promoviše upotrebu stvaranih obrazovnih alata za podučavanje medijske i informacijske pismenosti u visokom obrazovanju, a fokusom na podučavanje povjerenja u informacijskim naukaма. Ovaj obrazovni materijal nastao je u okviru Letnje škole u Barceloni, kao dio projekta GEDIS.

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© Bošković, Luka, Lejla Mulabećirović i Hajrija Osmanhodžić. 2025. Paradoksi medijske i informacijske pismenosti. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17333860
Sufinansirano od strane Evropske unije. Imenovanje i istaknuće uključuju suodgovornost autora i ne odražavaju nužno stavove Evropske unije ni Španske službe za internacionalizaciju obrazovanja (SEPPE). Evropska unija, niti njeno koga oblažuje sredstva, ne mogu se smatrati odgovornim za njih.

First version

Bošković, Luka, Mulabećirović, Lejla, Osmanhodžić, Hajrija. 2025. "Paradoksi medijske i informacijske pismenosti". <https://zenodo.org/records/17167799>

Derivative works and translations (OER's also included):

- ❖ Bošković, Luka, Lejla Mulabećirović, and Hajrija Osmanhodžić. 2025. "Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333860>

- ❖ San José, Claudia, and Juan-José Boté-Vericad. 2025. “Paradojas de la alfabetización mediática e informacional”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333950>
- ❖ San José, Claudia, and Juan-José Boté-Vericad. 2025. “Paradoxes de l'alfabetització mediàtica i informacional”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333941>
- ❖ Kartašová, Denisa. 2025. “Paradoxy mediální a informační gramotnosti”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333934>
- ❖ Karmil, Kenza. 2025. “Paradoxien der medien-und informationskompetenz”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333922>
- ❖ Martinović, Sara. 2025. “Paradoksi medijske i informacijski pismenosti”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333909>

Why as a prototype:

- Core information literacy / media and information literacy topic with a gender lens.
- Multilingual and easily integrated into introductory information and communication courses.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

2.2 User Experience and Gender

First version

Batlle, Ariadna, San José, Claudia. 2025. “Experiència d’usuari: UX”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333191>.

Derivative works and translations (OER’s also included):

- ❖ Batlle Belmonte, Ariadna, San José, Claudia. 2025. “Experiencia de la persona usuaria: UX”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333259>
- ❖ Batlle Belmonte, San José, Claudia. 2025. “User Experience: UX”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333324>
- ❖ Bitunjac, Marija. 2025. “Korisničko Iskustvo: UX”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333632>
- ❖ Osmanhodžić, Hajrija. 2025. “Korisničko iskustvo: UX”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333668>

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- ❖ Chlopčíková, Nela. 2025. “Uživatelská Zkušenost : UX”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333730>
- ❖ Varbanova, Daniela. 2025. “Die Nutzererfahrung”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333777>.

Why as a prototype:

- Connects gender with UX and user-centred design, a key area in LIS/IS.
- Ideal for practical activities (evaluating interfaces, detecting biases, etc.).

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

2.3 Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias

This OER comprises a poster and an evidence brief on the AI gender data gap—definition, causes, documented cases, and recommended interventions.

Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias

The gender data gap = missing/uneven data about women. As a result, AI decisions skew male through representative, algorithmic, cultural, and intersectional biases.

WHY IT HAPPENS

- Most AI teams are men; design choices reflect their blind spots.
- Training data under-represent women.
- Optimising only for overall accuracy or profit can sideline minorities.
- Women's phone/internet access is lower → fewer data traces.
- Binary labels and averages hides subgroups.

CASES BY BIAS TYPE

Representative

- Face recognition: 35% errors for darker-skinned women (0.8% lighter-skinned men).
- DALL·E 2 job images: women 38% (men 62%); women smiling 2.2x more.
- STEM visuals: 75-100% men.

Algorithmic

- Hiring AI: male-skewed training → women's CVs down-ranked.
- Credit scoring: women fewer/smaller loans despite better repayment.
- Health AI: misses women's symptoms → delayed diagnosis.
- Music recommenders: up to +6.3 pp more accurate for men.

Cultural

- Default female assistants → “women-as-helpers” stereotype.
- Llama-2 stories: women in domestic roles -4x more; men get higher-status jobs.

Intersectional

- YouTube captions: more errors for women.
- STEM job ads: men ~20% impressions.
- Book recommenders: less exposure for women authors

CLOSING THE GAP: WHAT TO DO

Representative bias

- Inclusive datasets; document & publish coverage; intersectional benchmarks.

Algorithmic bias

- Remove gender markers from inputs; adjust decision thresholds to balance errors; debias in training and post-processing; continuous monitoring.

Cultural bias

- Neutral/non-binary default voices; design checks for stereotypes; diverse teams in design and testing.

Intersectional bias

- Publish subgroup metrics (gender, skin tone, age, dialect); pre/post-deployment audits; classify HR/finance as high-risk; gender impact statements; transparency standards.

REFERENCES

John, Anna, Marcilla Iñes, and Ely Verena. “The Global Landscape of AI Ethics Guidelines.” *Nature Machine Intelligence* 1, no. 2 (September 2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0088-2>

UNESCO and IFLA. “Challenging Systemic Prejudice: An Investigation into Gender Bias in Large Language Models”, 2024. <https://www.unesco.org/ark:/48223/v000389571>

GEDIS project context

This resource is part of the European project GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), which promotes open educational tools to tackle gender inequalities in higher education, with an emphasis on disciplines related to Information and Library Science. This educational material was developed within the framework of the Summer School Barcelona, as part of the GEDIS project.

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First version

Bosshammer, Svetlana, Varbanova, Daniela. 2025. “Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17164102>.

Derivative works and translations (OER’s also included):

- ❖ Bosshammer, Svetlana, Varbanova, Daniela. 2025. “Mind the Gap: Genderdaten und KI-Bias”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17316168>
- ❖ San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Cuidado con la brecha: datos de género y sesgo de IA”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17316182>
- ❖ San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Compte amb la bretxa: dades de gènere i biaix d'IA”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17316245>
- ❖ Bošković, Luka. 2025. “Pazite na jaz: Rodni podaci i UI pristranost”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17292929>
- ❖ Gagulić, Kristina. 2025. “Pazite na jaz: Pristranost UI zbog razlika u podacima o spolu i rodu”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17285658>
- ❖ Chlopčíková, Nela. 2025. “Pozor na mezeru: Genderová data a předsudky v AI”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333105>

Why as a prototype:

- Core focus on data, algorithmic bias, and gender.
- Highly aligned with AI, data science, and information ethics.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

2.4 Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications, and Solutions

The thumbnail shows the GEDIS logo on the left. To its right is the title 'Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications, and Solutions' in bold black text, underlined with a yellow line. Below the title is a short description: 'This OER examines AI and algorithmic bias, its causes, and real-world impacts. It highlights the importance of human oversight and strategies to mitigate bias for fairer AI systems.' At the bottom, there is a blue-bordered box containing two definitions: 'Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to systems that display intelligent behavior by analyzing their environment and taking actions – with some degree of autonomy – to achieve specific goals.' and 'Algorithmic bias is a systematic error or unfair outcome produced by machine learning algorithms, often reflecting or reinforcing existing social, racial, or gender biases, caused by prejudiced assumptions in their design or by training on incomplete or distorted data.'

First version

Karmil, Kenza, Boskovic, Luka, Kartášová, Denisa. 2025. "Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications, and Solutions". Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17067091>.

Derivative works and translations (OER's also included):

- ❖ San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Biaix algorítmic en la IA: conceptes clau, implicacions i solucions”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17306646>
- ❖ San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Sesgo algorítmico en la IA: conceptos clave, implicaciones y soluciones”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296079>
- ❖ Kenza, Karmil. 2025. “Algorithmische Voreingenommenheit in der KI: Zentrale Konzepte, Implikationen und Lösungen”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17166835>
- ❖ Bošković, Luka. 2025. “Algoritamska pristranost u UI: Ključni pojmovi, implikacije, i rješenja”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293326>
- ❖ Bitunjac, Marija. 2025. “Algoritamska pristranost u umjetnoj inteligenciji: Ključni pojmovi, implikacije i rješenja”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17164519>
- ❖ Kartašová, Denisa. 2025. “Algoritmičká zaujatost v umělé inteligenci: Klíčové pojmy, dopady a řešení”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17302342>

Why as a prototype:

- Complements the previous one, but with a stronger focus on key concepts, implications, and solutions.
- Perfect as a theory–practice module in information technology courses.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

2.5 Students' Perception on Using ChatGPT for Educational Purposes and Gender Differences

Percepcija studenata o korištenju ChatGPT-a za obrazovne svrhe i rodne razlike

ChatGPT studentima je omogućio personalizirano učenje i generiranje sadržaja čime je izazvao promjene u navikama i načinu učenja kod studenata. Zbog takvih promjena provedena su istraživanja studenata o korištenju i percepciji ChatGPT-a u obrazovne svrhe te rodnim razlikama.

Percepcija Studenata o korištenju ChatGPT-a u obrazovne svrhe

POZITIVNI ASPEKTI

- personalizirano učenje
- širok raspon informacija
- jednostavnost upotrebe
- višejezičnost
- ušteta vremena
- brzina generiranja sadržaja

NEGATIVNI ASPEKTI

- kvaliteta i pouzdanost izvora
- lažne reference
- nepravilna uporaba idioma
- matematički izrazi

Kako ukloniti negativnosti?

Razlike u percepciji korisnosti i korištenju ChatGPT-a

♀	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • kraće korištenje po sesiji ali učestalije • manje percipiran kao koristan i jednostavan • viša zabrinutost oko rizika
♂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • duže korištenje po sesiji ali manje učestalo • više percipiran kao koristan i jednostavan • manja zabrinutost oko rizika

Što mislite zašto postoje ove razlike u percepciji i korištenju?

LITERATURA

Bitunjac, Marija, Sara Martinović i Lorena Brtan. 2025. "Percepcija studenata o korištenju ChatGPT-a za obrazovne svrhe i rodne razlike." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17012884>

Veza sa GEDIS projektom

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First version

Bitunjac, Marija, Martinović, Sara, Brtan, Lorena. 2025. "Percepcija studenata o korištenju ChatGPT-a za obrazovne svrhe i rodne razlike." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17012884>.

Derivative works and translations (OER's also included):

- ❖ Bitunjac, Marija, Martinović, Sara, Brtan, Lorena. 2025. "Students' perception on using ChatGPT for educational purposes and gender differences." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17306856>
- ❖ San José, Claudia, Battle, Ariadna. 2025. "Precepción del estudiantado sobre el uso de ChatGPT con fines educativos y diferencias de género." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17306905>

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<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

- ❖ San José, Claudia, Batlle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. "Precepció de l'estudiantat sobre l'ús de ChatGPT amb finalitats educatius i diferències de gènere." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17318284>
- ❖ Koçlu, Burcu. 2025. "Studierendenwahrnehmung der Nutzung von ChatGPT im Bildungsbereich und geschlechtsspezifische Unterschiede." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17302547>
- ❖ Varga, Izabela. 2025. "Jak studenti vnímají používání ChatGPT v oblasti vzdělávání a rozdílů v pohlaví." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17318236>
- ❖ Mulabećirović, Lejla. 2025. "Percepcija studenata o korištenju ChatGPT-a u obrazovne svrhe i rodne razlike." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17292772>

Why as a prototype:

- Brings together generative AI, student practices, and gender.
- A good prototype for debate activities, in-class surveys, and case analysis.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

2.6 Gaming and Gender

Videigre i spol

Ovaj OER prikazuje glavne izazove, prednosti i rješenja vezana uz spol i videoigre, s posebnim naglaskom na iskustva i prikazivanje žena. Ističe utjecaj stereotipa, seksizma i toksičnosti zajednice, ali i pozitivne učinke raznolikosti i inkluzivnog dizajna videoigara. Cilj mu je naglasiti ključne izazove, mogućnosti i rješenja vezana uz spol i videoigre kako bi se potaklo stvaranje inkluzivnijeg i kreativnijeg okruženja za sve igrače.

<p>Povijest i kontekst</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • industrija videoigara od samih početaka oblikovana u muškom okruženju - razvila kulturu u kojoj dominira muška perspektiva • videoigre stvarane za mušku publiku • razlike u navikama, motivacijama i iskustvima igranja 	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: left;"> <p>kasnije počinju igrati</p> <p>manje sati tjedno</p> <p>kreativnost, društvenost, prilagodba</p> <p>češće izbjegavaju toksične zajednice</p> </div> </div>	<p>Prikaz žena u videoigrama</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nemoćni ili sekundarni likovi • često prikazani u ulozi "damsel in distress" • seksualizirani prikazi žena u videoigrama povezani s nižim samopouzdanjem igračica i jačanjem seksističkih stavova kod igrača
<p>Izazovi</p> <p>Stereotipi, toksično ponašanje, seksualizacija, stvaranje krivih percepcija...</p>	<p>Prednosti</p> <p>Raznolikost, inkluzivnost, kreativnost, smanjivanje stereotipa, ravnopravnost...</p>	<p>Rješenja</p> <p>Inkluzivni dizajn, promjene u industrijskoj praksi, edukacije i prevencije stereotipa</p>

Ciljna grupa: Studenti/ke

LITERATURA

Gabriel-Perez, Julia, Manuel Merit-Villar, Cesar Merino-Soto, Guillermo M. Cham, i Laura Badenes-Ellena. 2024. Gender differences in internet gaming among university students: a diachronic analysis. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.23918/ps.v2i204.1612730>

Pan, Ruiqi. 2023. Video Games and Gender Equality: How Has Video Gaming Become a Male Privilege? DOI: <https://doi.org/10.55554/2.732.735652929026>

Veza sa GEDIS projektom

Ovaj je resurs dio evropskog projekta GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), koji promiče stvaranje obrazovne okoline za uključivanje mladih nepredstavici u visokoškolskom obrazovanju, s naglaskom na disciplinu znanosti i informacijama i inženjerskim znanostima. Ovaj je obrazovni materijal razvijen u okviru Ujedinjene škole u Barceloni, kao dio projekta GEDIS.

GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education. <https://ub.edu/gedis>

Ciljna grupa: Gagulić, Kristina, Inga Pemper, Antonio Prgomet, 2025. Videigre i spol. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17315482

Sufinancirano od strane Evropske unije. Umešano mišljenje i stavovi isključivo su odgovornost autora i ne odražavaju ništa stavove Evropske unije niti Španjolske službe za internacionalizaciju obrazovanja (SEPE), Evropske unije, niti tijelo koje dopušta sredstva, ne mogu se smatrati odgovornim za njih.

First version

Gagulić, Kristina, Pemper, Inga, Prgomet, Antonio. 2025. "Videigre i spol". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17315482>.

Derivative works and translations (OER's also included):

- ❖ Gagulić, Kristina, Pemper, Inga, Prgomet, Antonio. 2025. "Gaming & Gender". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17315515>
- ❖ Min, Hyerim. 2025. "Gaming und Gender". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17332891>
- ❖ San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. "Videojuegos y Género". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17332914>

**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
Challenges in Higher Education**

Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

- ❖ Batlle, Ariadna Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Videojocs i gènere”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17332969>
- ❖ Bošković, Luka. 2025. “Video-igre & spol”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333002>.
- ❖ Kartašová, Denisa. 2025. “Videohry & Gender”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333030>

Why as a prototype:

- Appealing topic for students, with a clear component of stereotypes and representation.
- Fits very well with the use of the serious game and game-based learning.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education

Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

2.7 Cultural Heritage and Gender

Cultural Heritage and Gender

This project explores how cultural heritage, particularly in the field of literature, has historically marginalized women (authors) and their works. It highlights forgotten female voices and proposes strategies to ensure a more inclusive cultural memory for future generations – canon revision, re-editions, translations, and digital projects.

Target audiences: 🧑 Students

- Introduction + historically imbalanced canon
- Forgotten voices and their rediscovery
- The present, libraries and the audience

legacy compiled of artifacts and attributes of a particular group or society

draws from the past and aims to benefit the future generations

concept of cultural heritage is changing based on current cultural systems and their values

First version

Chlopčíková, Nela, Kartášová, Denisa, Varga, Izabela. 2025. “Cultural Heritage and Gender”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17145145>.

Derivative works and translations (OER’s also included):

- ❖ San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Patrimoni Cultural i Gènere”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328759>
- ❖ Batlle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Patrimonio Cultural y Género”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328727>
- ❖ Bosshammer, Svetlana. 2025. “Kulturelles Erbe und Gender”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17303403>
- ❖ Osmanhodžić, Hajrija. 2025. “Kulturno naslijeđe i rod”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17256108>

GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education

Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

- ❖ Pemper, Inga. 2025. “Kulturna baština i rod”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17256271>
- ❖ Chlopčíková, Nela, Kartašová, Denisa, Varga, Izabela. 2025. “Kulturní dědictví a gender”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17318453>

Why as a prototype:

- Covers the GLAM + gender dimension, very much in line with your areas of work.
- Transferable to courses on heritage, historical documentation, museology, etc.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

2.8 Translation and Gender

GEDIS

This OER explores the intersections of translation and gender, focusing on feminist translation practices, gendered language, and cross-linguistic challenges. It aims to help students critically engage with language and develop inclusive translation strategies.

Target audience: Students

Feminist Translation	Traditional Translation	LLM Translation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ideological act; translator = rewriter • Example: "...without opening legs" • Strategies: supplementing, prefacing/footnoting, hijacking • Challenges patriarchy → empowers women, develops language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neutral, faithful copy; passive, inferior • Example: "...without pulling up skirt" • Metaphors of reproduction, control, violence • Maintains patriarchal stereotypes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most systems default to masculine forms in ambiguous cases. • Systems default to stereotypical gender roles in professions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Doctor → doctor (masculine) ◦ Nurse → enfermera (feminine) • Machine translation can reflect and even exacerbate existing biases. • Responsibility of translators and developers: develop strategies for more neutral and inclusive translations.

Gendered	vs.	Gender-Neutral
Chairman Fireman Policeman	→	Chairperson Firefighter Police officer
Bilimadani (science man)	→	Bilim insani (science person)
Studenten Lehrer	→	Studierende Lehrkräfte
Zdravotní sestra (nurse working as a nurse)	→	Zdravotní sestra / bratr (just a nurse)

Cross-linguistic Gender Challenges

- Translation = more than words. It shapes and reproduces gender ideologies.
- Translators = not neutral mediators. They are active agents making ideological choices.
- Choices in pronouns, inclusivity, visibility = political acts

LLM - Strategies

- Gender-neutral adjectives (e.g., forms for both masculine and feminine).
- Neuter case adjectives (use of neuter grammar in Icelandic/Czech).
- Part of speech change (using a noun phrase instead of an adjective).
- English borrowing (keeping the adjective in English).
- Alternative morphology (e.g., in Spanish replacing -o/-a with @).

REFERENCES

- Ondoro-Soler, Nerea, and Mikal L. Forcada. "The Exacerbation of Grammatical Gender Stereotypes in English-Spanish Machine Translation." *Traducción: tecnologías de la traducción*, no. 20 (December 15, 2020): 176-191. <https://doi.org/10.5209/115565>
- Lúcia van Flinck, 1995. *Feminist Translation: Contexts, Practices and Theories*. <https://www.leeds.ac.uk/artsandsocialsciences/115565>
- Hillary Dawkins, Işar Huseynli, and Chi Kiu Lu. 2025. *Gender Neutral Machine Translation Strategies in Practice*. In *Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Gender Inclusive Translation Technologies (GIT 2025)*, pages 74-86. Geneva, Switzerland: European Association for Machine Translation. <https://aclanthology.org/2025.git.1.5.pdf>

GEDIS project context

This resource is part of the European project GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), which promotes open educational tools to tackle gender inequalities in higher education, with an emphasis on disciplines related to Information and Library Science. This educational material was developed within the framework of the Summer School Barcelona, as part of the GEDIS project.

GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education. <https://ub.edu/gedis>

Citation: Buncu Raicu, Piromeni Antonia, Varga Izabela. 2025. Translation and Gender. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1706271

Co-funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Spanish Service for the Internationalisation of Education (SIEPE). Neither the EU nor the granting authority can be held responsible.

First version

Koçlu, Burcu, Prgomet, Antonio, Varga, Izabela. 2025. “Translation and Gender”.
Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17062711>.

Derivative works and translations (OER’s also included):

- ❖ Koçlu, Burcu. 2025. “Übersetzung und Gender”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17301443>
- ❖ Prgoment, Antonio. 2025. “Prevođenje i spol”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17285375>
- ❖ San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Traducción y género”.
Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293767>
- ❖ San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Traducció i gènere”.
Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17301563>
- ❖ Bošković, Luka. 2025. “Prevođenje i rod”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293130>
- ❖ Varga, Izabela. 2025. “Překlad a gender”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17301523>

Why as a prototype:

- Excellent for working on inclusive language, representation, and biases in translation.
- Also useful as a cross-cutting resource for any course that uses multilingual texts.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

2.9 Hate Speech & Mis/Disinformation

Hate Speech & Mis/Disinformation

*The real status or treatment of
women within socialist contexts*

This open educational resource (OER) offers a historical perspective on the invisible façades of totalitarianism and the role of women within it. It aims to encourage critical reflection on the power of hate speech, misinformation and disinformation as tools of propaganda used to shape ideology and suppress dissent.

Target audiences: 📖 Librarians, 👨 Professors, 🎓 Students

1. KEY CONCEPTS (DEFINITIONS)

- Hate speech, misinformation, and disinformation are distinct forms of harmful speech
- No universally agreed-upon definitions for these terms
- Definitions vary across legal, academic, and policy contexts

Hate Speech

Any kind of communication in speech, writing, or behavior, that attacks or uses pejorative or discriminatory language with reference to a person or a group on the basis of who they are — in other words, based on their religion, ethnicity, nationality, race, color, descent, gender, or other identity factor.

Misinformation vs. Disinformation

Misinformation refers to the unintentional spread of false or misleading information, while disinformation is the deliberate creation and dissemination of falsehoods intended to cause harm.

First version

Varbanova, Daniela, Gagulić, Kristina, Mulabećirović, Lejla. 2025. “Hate Speech & Mis/Disinformation: The real status or treatment of women within socialist contexts”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17067560>.

Derivative works and translations (OER’s also included):

- ❖ Battle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Discurso de odio y desinformación: El estatus real o el trato de las mujeres en contextos socialistas”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293659>
- ❖ Battle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Discurs d'odi i de desinformació”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17298272>

- ❖ Varbanova, Daniela. 2025. “Hassrede und Des-/Fehlinformation”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300493>
- ❖ Mulabećirović, Lejla. 2025. “Govor mržnje i mis/dezinformacije: Pravi status ili tretman žena u socijalističkim kontekstima”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300553>
- ❖ Gagulić, Kristina. 2025. “Govor mržnje i mis/dezinformacije”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300602>
- ❖ Kartašová, Denisa. 2025. “Nenávistné prejavy a mis/dezinformace: Skutečný stav nebo zacházení se ženami v rámci socialistických kontextů”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300649>

Why as a prototype:

- Connects disinformation, hate speech, and gender, directly aligned with your future TRUST-INFO lines.
- Very powerful as a prototype for critical analysis activities on news, corpora, etc.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
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<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

2.10 Supporting Women in Intro CS/IT

Supporting Women in Intro CS/IT

First-Two-Weeks Faculty Playbook

Target audiences: 🧑 Professors 🧑 Students

This open educational resource (OER) presents comparative data on gender representation in educational leadership across six European countries involved in the GEDIS project. Drawing on UNESCO's GEM Gender Report 2025, the infographic highlights disparities in the presence of women in ministerial positions, school leadership, and higher education management. The aim is to encourage critical reflection on gender inequalities in decision-making roles within the education sector.

Women in tech continue to face major inequality, from lower salaries and underrepresentation in leadership to limited access to venture capital. Despite claims of fair hiring and pay practices, real progress remains slow due to persistent barriers like stereotypes, lack of mentors, and pedagogical approaches. A practical toolkit with concrete strategies is essential to drive real change and foster a more inclusive tech industry.

Two-week Instructor Kit

First version

Bosshammer, Svetlana, Pemper, Inga, Bitunjac, Marija. 2025. "Supporting Women in Intro CS/IT: First-Two-Weeks Faculty Playbook". Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17067105>

Derivative works and translations (OER's also included):

- ❖ Batlle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. "Apoyando a las mujeres en cursos introductorios de Ciencias de la Computación/Tecnología de la Información: Manual para el profesorado para las dos primeras semanas". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293881>
- ❖ Batlle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. "Donant suport a les dones en cursos introductoris de Ciències de la Computació/Tecnologia de la Informació". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17306577>
- ❖ Bosshammer, Svetlana. 2025. "Frauen in Intro CS/IT unterstützen". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17166593>

- ❖ Osmanhodžić, Hajrija. 2025. “Podrška ženama u uvodnom CS/IT: Priručnik za nastavno osoblje za prve dvije sedmice”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17285428>
- ❖ Pemper, Inga. 2025. “Podrška ženama u računalnim znanostima/IT: Priručnik za nastavnike za prva dva tjedna”. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17285547>
- ❖ Chlopčíková, Nela. 2025. “Podpora žen v Intro CS/IT: Příručka pro fakulty v prvních dvou týdnech”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17302283>

Why as a prototype:

- It is clearly a teaching intervention resource (a playbook for lecturers).
- Fits perfectly as a prototypical method for introductory courses with a gender focus.

The OERs in this package were initially created by student teams during the GEDIS Summer School and subsequently revised and validated by lecturers to be used as reusable teaching materials.

**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
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Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

Co-funded by
the European Union

2.11 Women in Science and Engineering in the EU

Women in Science and Engineering in the EU: Where Do They Work and How Is Their Presence Evolving?

Data by sector (2023) with a gender perspective.

This open educational resource presents a comparative overview of the presence of women scientists and engineers in different sectors of the EU, based on Eurostat data (2023). It supports gender-focused analysis of structural inequalities in the academic teaching context.

Chart 1: Women scientists and engineers by sector (EU, 2023)

First version

Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Mandl, Thomas, Dreisiebner, Stefan, Khattab, Dzejla, Cupar, Drahomira, Dombrovská, Michaela, Badurina, Boris. 2025. “Women in Science and Engineering in the EU”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15108435>.

Derivative works and translations (OER's also included):

- ❖ Dombrovská, Michaela, Magdaléna Lapúniková, and Juan-José Boté-Vericad. “Ženy ve vědě a technice v EU: kde pracují a jak se jejich zastoupení vyvíjí?”. April 21, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15257877>.
- ❖ Petr Balog, Kornelija, Boris Badurina, Kristina Feldvari, Milijana Mićunović, Drahomira Cupar, Martina Dragija Ivanović, Zrinka Džoić, and Alica Kolarić.

“Žene u znanosti i inženjerstvu u EU”. April 11, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15195226>.

- ❖ Khattab, Džejlja, Lejla Hajdarpašić, Lamija Silajdžić, Nadina Grebović-Lendo, and Alma Mešić. “Žene u nauci i inženjerstvu u EU”. April 10, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15186762>.

- ❖ Mandl, Thomas, Sylvia Jaki, Stefan Dreisiebner, and Eithne Knappitsch. “Frauen in wissenschaft und technik in der EU”. April 9, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15185639>.

- ❖ Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Anna Villarroya, Mari Váñez, Maddalena Fedele, CAROLINA MARTÍN, Concepción FUENTES MORENO, Ruth Sofia Contreras-Espinosa, and Lydia Sánchez. “Dones en la ciència i l'enginyeria a la UE”. March 30, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15108381>.

- ❖ Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Anna Villarroya, Mari Váñez, Maddalena Fedele, Carolina Martín-Piñol, Concepción Fuentes, Ruth Sofia Contreras-Espinosa, and Lydia Sánchez. “Mujeres en la ciencia e ingeniería en la UE”. March 27, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15095020>.

Why as a prototype:

- Very clear prototype focused on official data, visualisation, and gap analysis.
- Facilitates quantitative activities and international comparison.

2.12 Methodological Prototypes (Research & Evaluation)

OERs included:

**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
Challenges in Higher Education**

Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

Co-funded by
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2.12.1. Curriculum Analysis Rubric — Gender Perspectives in Teaching Plans

Curriculum Analysis Rubric — Gender Perspectives in Teaching Plans

This open educational resource (OER) offers a rubric for analyzing teaching plans from a gender perspective in Bachelor's and Master's degrees. It has been used in the field of Library and Information Science but can also be applied in other fields. It includes instructions for use, observable criteria, and a template (xlsx/csv/odt) for data collection. It is accompanied by a teaching note.

Target audiences: Librarians, Professors, quality/equality managers, qualification teams

Main Sections

📌 Course identification

- Programme, course.
- University.
- Type of course.
- Teaching staff gender.

📖 Gender in Course Content

- Mentions of gender, diversity & inclusivity.
- References to SDGs.
- Integration into objectives, competencies, and thematic blocks.

Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Stefan Dreisiebner, Džejlja Khattab, Kornelija Petr Balog, Thomas Mandl, Michaela Dombrovská, and Drahomira Cupar. “Curriculum Analysis Rubric — Gender Perspectives in Teaching Plans”.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16785974>

This OER is provided only in English.

2.12.2. What data are you collecting? Inclusive Perspectives in Gender-Focused Research

GEDIS **WHAT DATA ARE YOU COLLECTING?**
Inclusive Perspectives in Gender-Focused Research

Why collect sociodemographic data?

- Reveal structural inequalities
- Reflect the diversity of identities
- Design policies and actions based on evidence
- Improve research quality through intersectionality

How to ask inclusive questions?

- What gender identity do you identify with (open/multiple choice)
- Avoid binary options only ("Male / Female")
- Allow self-definition ("Other - please specify")
- Include "Prefer not to answer"

Target audiences: Librarians, Professors, Students

KEY CATEGORIES & EXAMPLES

Sex / Gender	Assigned sex at birth, gender identity
Age	Use age ranges relevant to the study
Ethnic origin	Avoid imprecise or colonial terms; allow self-identification
Disability	Ask about functional situation, not medical diagnosis
Sexual orientation	Always optional and anonymous
Educational level	Use categories compatible with national or international systems
Socioeconomic situation	Income, occupation, housing, etc.

Real examples: Student survey: Delphi Study in GEDIS project

Ethical tips & practises

- Ensure confidentiality
- Get informed consent
- Avoid forcing responses
- Raise awareness if sensitive topics are addressed

What is the data for?

- Improve design study
- Adapt teaching materials
- Build gender-focused indicators
- Influence inclusive policies

Intersectional lens
Combine gender with race, class, disability, age, and migrant identity to understand complex realities.

REFERENCES
Siler, Sebastian, Johannes Breuer, Pascal Slegers, and Kjerskin Thorsen. 2020. "Integrating Survey Data and Digital Trace Data: Key Issues in Developing an Emerging Field." *Social Science Computer Review* 38 (8): 502-410. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894439319843669>
Villarroya, Anna, and Juan-José Boté-Vericad. 2023. "The Gender and LGBTQ Perspectives in Library and Information Science: A Case Study at the University of Barcelona." *Library & Information Science Research* 45 (3): 101238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lis.2023.101238>

GEDIS project context
This resource is part of the European project GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), which promotes open educational tools to tackle gender inequalities in higher education, with an emphasis on disciplines related to information and library science.

GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education. <https://ub.edu/gedis>
Citation: Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Thomas Mandl, Dreisiebner, Stefan, Silajdžić, Martina Dragija, Magdaléna Lapúniková, and Boris Badurina. 2025. "What data are you collecting? Inclusive Perspectives in Gender-Focused Research." DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15397953

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First version

Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Thomas Mandl, Dreisiebner, Stefan, Silajdžić, Lamija, Dragija Ivanović, Martina, Lapúniková, Magdaléna, & Badurina, Boris. 2025. "What data are you collecting? Inclusive Perspectives in Gender-Focused Research". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15397953>

Derivative works and translations (OER's also included):

- ❖ Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Anna Villarroya, Maddalena Fedele, Carolina Martín-Piñol, Concepción Fuentes Moreno, Ruth Contreras-Espinosa, Mari Váñez, and Lydia Sánchez. "¿qué datos están recopilando? perspectivas inclusivas en la

investigación con enfoque de género”. June 15, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15666130> .

- ❖ Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Anna Villarroya, Maddalena Fedele, Carolina Martín-Piñol, Concepción Fuentes Moreno, Ruth Sofia Contreras-Espinosa, Mari Vállez, and Lydia Sánchez. “Quines dades esteu recollint? perspectives inclusives en la recerca amb perspectiva de gènere”. June 14, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15665246>.
- ❖ Mandl, Thomas, and Stefan Dreisiebner. “Welche daten werden erhoben? inklusive perspektiven in der geschlechtersensiblen forschung”. May 30, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771643>.
- ❖ Khattab, Džejla, Lejla Hajdarpašić, and Lamija Silajdžić. “Koje podatke prikupljate? inkluzivne perspektive u istraživanjima fokusiranim na rod”. May 23, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15471317>.
- ❖ Petr Balog, Kornelija, Martina Dragija Ivanović, Kristina Feldvari, and Milijana Micunovic. “Koje podatke prikupljate? inkluzivne perspektive u istraživanju usmjerenom na rod”. May 22, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15492477>.
- ❖ Dombrovská, Michaela, and Magdaléna Lapúniková. “Jaká data shromažďujete? inkluzivní přístupy v genderově zaměřeném výzkumu”. June 2, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15579151> .

Why as a prototype:

- It shows concretely **how to design data collection in a gender-inclusive way** (variables, categories, wording, sampling, ethics).
- It turns the rather abstract idea of “including gender” into **very practical decisions** (what we ask, to whom, how we record answers, how we code identity, etc.).

2.12.3. Delphi Method in Academic Research: A Step-by-Step Guide for Faculty Members

Delphi Method in Academic Research: A Step-by-Step Guide for faculty members

This open educational resource (OER) presents a structured overview of the Delphi Method in academic research. It supports the development of gender-aware, consensus-driven approaches in teaching, policy design, and institutional change.

What is the Delphi Method?

A research survey technique used to collect experts' opinions on a specific topic, developed for systematic forecasting to achieve consensus.

When to Use it?

- Policy development
- Curriculum design
- Technology foresight
- Gender-sensitive institutional change

Core Characteristics

- Iterative rounds
- Anonymity of experts
- Controlled feedback
- Statistical aggregation of responses

First version

Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Jaki, Sylvia, Khattab, Dzejla, Džoić, Zrinka, Dombrovská, Michaela, & Petr Balog, Kornelija. 2025. "Delphi Method in Academic Research: A Step-by-Step Guide for faculty members". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15260706>.

Derivative works and translations (OER's also included):

- Delphi metoda u akademskom istraživanju: vodič korak po korak za sveučilišno nastavno osoblje. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15529712>.

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- ❖ El Método Delphi en la Investigación Académica: Guía Paso a Paso para el Personal Docente Universitario. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15284153>.
- ❖ Delfská metoda v akademickém výzkumu: Průvodce krok za krokem pro členy fakulty. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15283077>.
- ❖ El mètode Delphi en la recerca acadèmica: guia pas a pas per al professorat universitari. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15284099>.
- ❖ Delphi metoda u akademskim istraživanjima: Korak po korak vodič za univerzitetsko nastavno osoblje. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15312587>.
- ❖ Die Delphi-Methode in der akademischen Forschung: Schritt-für-Schritt-Anleitung für Hochschullehrende. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15284004>.

Why as a prototype:

- They provide the methodological backbone: how to conduct research and evaluation with a gender perspective.
- They fit very well with WP3 and with the idea of “tools” within Result 3.

3. Teaching Prototype Packages

3.1 Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy

Thematic focus

Paradoxes and tensions in media and information literacy (MIL) from a gender-aware perspective, including neutrality, trust, responsibility and representation in digital media environments.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Undergraduate students in LIS, communication and media studies (2nd–4th year);
Master’s students interested in MIL, journalism, or digital culture.

Approximate duration

60–90 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

Basic understanding of media and information literacy; familiarity with social media and news platforms.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, learners will be able to:

- Explain what is meant by “paradoxes” in media and information literacy.
- Identify how claims of neutrality and objectivity may obscure gendered biases.

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- Analyse media or information artefacts using a MIL and gender lens.
- Reflect on their own responsibilities as consumers and producers of information.

Core OER(s) included

- Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy (English)
- Paradojas de la alfabetización mediática e informacional (Spanish)
- Paradoxes de l'alfabetització mediàtica i informacional (Catalan)
- Paradoxy mediální a informační gramotnosti (Czech)
- Paradoxien der Medien-und Informationskompetenz (German)
- Paradoksi medijske i informacijske pismenosti (Bosnian)
- Paradoksi medijske i informacijski pismenosti (Croatian)

Additional materials needed

Projector and internet access; 2–3 short media items (news articles, social media posts, campaign materials) selected by the teacher.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Short brainstorming: students list situations where they expected “neutral” information (e.g. encyclopaedias, news bulletins) but later discovered bias or manipulation. Introduce the OER and its paradoxes (neutrality, trust, responsibility).

Core activity / exploration (30–40 minutes)

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In groups, students read the relevant OER section in their preferred language. Each group receives a different media item and is asked to identify:

- how neutrality is constructed or claimed,
- whose voices are amplified or silenced,
- how gender is represented or absent.

Groups summarise their findings on a poster or shared slide.

Synthesis and reflection (15–20 minutes)

Groups present their analyses. The teacher guides a discussion on how MIL education can address these paradoxes without reproducing them. The class co-creates a short checklist for “gender-and MIL-aware” media consumption.

Optional extension / homework

Short reflective essay or blog-style post in which students apply the paradox framework to a media channel they follow regularly.

Assessment and evaluation

Formative assessment based on group presentations and participation; optional short written reflection graded with a simple rubric (clarity, use of concepts, critical insight).

Links to curricula and potential courses

Media and Information Literacy; Introduction to Communication; Digital Culture and Society; Journalism and Ethics.

Suggestions for adaptation

Can be run with a single media item in shorter sessions; can be used online with shared documents and breakout rooms; media items can be tailored to local contexts or current events.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.2 Teaching Prototype Package – User Experience and Gender (User Experience: UX)

Thematic focus

User experience (UX), usability and interface evaluation in LIS and digital environments, with specific attention to gendered experiences and inclusivity.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Undergraduate LIS and information management students; students in human-computer interaction, UX, or digital library courses.

Approximate duration

90 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

Introductory knowledge of information systems or digital platforms; basic familiarity with UX concepts is helpful but not essential.

Learning outcomes

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- After completing this activity, learners will be able to:
- Describe key principles of user-centred and inclusive design.
- Identify potential gender-related barriers in digital interfaces.
- Apply simple UX evaluation criteria to library or information systems.
- Propose improvements to make interfaces more inclusive.

Core OER(s) included

- Experiència d'usuari: UX (Catalan)
- Experiencia de la persona usuaria: UX (Spanish)
- User Experience: UX (English)
- Korisničko iskustvo: UX (Bosnian)
- Korisničko Iskustvo: UX (Croatian)
- Uživatelská zkušenost: UX (Czech)
- Die Nutzererfahrung (German)

Additional materials needed

Access to one or two real interfaces (OPAC, discovery tool, institutional repository, or website); printed evaluation checklist based on the OER.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Students briefly share positive and negative experiences with library or academic platforms. Teacher introduces the UX OER and highlights its gender-sensitive perspective.

Core activity / exploration (40–45 minutes)

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In small groups, students use the OER to derive or refine UX evaluation criteria (navigation, language, representation, accessibility, inclusivity). They then evaluate one chosen platform, taking notes on issues that may affect different user groups, including women and gender-diverse users.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Groups present 2–3 key problems and suggested improvements. A plenary discussion links these findings to professional roles and responsibilities in LIS.

Optional extension / homework

Students document their evaluation in a short report or screencast, which can be reused as teaching material or as input for local UX improvement projects.

Assessment and evaluation

Assessment can be based on group UX reports or presentations; optional individual reflection on how UX intersects with gender and inclusion.

Links to curricula and potential courses

User Studies; Human–Computer Interaction; Digital Libraries; Web Design for Information Services.

Suggestions for adaptation

For online teaching, students can evaluate interfaces from home and collaborate via shared documents; for shorter sessions, focus on a very small set of criteria.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.3 Teaching Prototype Package - Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias

Thematic focus

Gender data gaps and their impact on algorithmic bias in AI and information systems.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Undergraduate LIS and information science students (2nd–4th year); Master's students in information science, communication or data-related programmes.

Approximate duration

90 minutes (can be split into 2 × 45 minutes).

Required prior knowledge

Basic understanding of how digital platforms and AI systems process data; introductory knowledge of information literacy and critical evaluation of information sources.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, learners will be able to:

- Describe what is meant by “gender data gap” and why it matters.
- Explain how missing or biased gender data can lead to discriminatory outcomes in AI systems.
- Critically analyse simple examples of datasets, interfaces or algorithms from a gender perspective.

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- Propose basic strategies to mitigate gender bias in data collection and AI-based services in LIS contexts.

Core OER(s) included

- Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias (English)
- Mind the Gap: Genderdaten und KI-Bias (German)
- Cuidado con la brecha: datos de género y sesgo de IA (Spanish)
- Compte amb la bretxa: dades de gènere i biaix d'IA (Catalan)
- Pazite na jaz: Rodni podaci i UI pristranost (Bosnian)
- Pazite na jaz: Pristranost UI zbog razlika u podacima o spolu i rodu (Croatian)
- Pozor na mezeru: Genderová data a předsudky v AI (Czech)

Additional materials needed

- Projector and internet access.
- Printed or digital copies of the OER in the appropriate teaching language.
- 1–2 short case descriptions or screenshots of real systems (e.g. recommendation systems, recruitment tools, search interfaces) showing possible gender bias.
- Optional: small synthetic dataset with missing or unbalanced gender variables.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up (10–15 minutes):

Short whole-class discussion: ask students to recall any news story or example where AI or digital systems were accused of being “biased” or “unfair”. Introduce the idea of gender data gaps and link it to their examples.

Core activity – Reading and group analysis (35–40 minutes):

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In small groups, students read the OER section that explains gender data gaps and AI bias. Each group receives a different short case or mini-dataset and is asked to identify where gender data are missing, underrepresented or stereotyped, and how this might affect the outcome of the system. Groups prepare a brief poster or slide summarising their findings.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes):

Groups present their findings. The teacher moderates a discussion connecting the cases to broader issues of fairness, accountability and professional responsibility in LIS. The class jointly drafts a short list of “basic principles” for gender-aware data practices in libraries, archives or information platforms.

Optional extension / homework:

Individually or in pairs, students select a digital service they use regularly (e.g. streaming platform, social media, search engine) and write a short reflection on where gender data might be used, missing or biased, and what improvements could be proposed.

Assessment and evaluation:

Formative assessment based on the quality of group analysis and participation in discussions.

Optionally, a short written reflection (300–500 words) in which students apply the concepts to a system of their choice, assessed with a brief rubric (clarity of explanation, correct use of concepts, depth of reflection, connection to practice).

Links to curricula and potential courses:

- Information Literacy / Media and Information Literacy.
- Data and Society / Ethics of Information and AI.
- Introduction to Data Management in LIS.

- User Studies and Digital Platforms.

Suggestions for adaptation

- For larger groups, increase the number of cases and reduce reporting time per group.
- For shorter sessions (45–60 minutes), focus only on one case study and the plenary discussion.
- For online teaching, use breakout rooms for group work and collaborative documents (e.g. shared slides or whiteboards) for reporting.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.4 Teaching Prototype Package – Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications, and Solutions

Thematic focus

Core concepts of algorithmic bias in AI, implications for justice and inclusion, and possible mitigation strategies in information systems.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Advanced undergraduate and Master’s students in LIS, data science, digital humanities, or related fields.

Approximate duration

90–120 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

Basic understanding of algorithms and AI-based systems; introductory knowledge of data and information ethics.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, learners will be able to:

- Define algorithmic bias and distinguish it from simple error or noise.
- Identify different sources of bias in AI systems (data, models, interfaces).
- Relate algorithmic bias to gender, race and other intersecting categories.
- Outline practical strategies for reducing bias in LIS-related contexts.

Core OER(s) included

- Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications, and Solutions (English)
- Biaix algorítmic en la IA: conceptes clau, implicacions i solucions (Catalan)
- Sesgo algorítmico en la IA: conceptos clave, implicaciones y soluciones (Spanish)
- Algorithmische Voreingenommenheit in der KI: Zentrale Konzepte, Implikationen und Lösungen (German)
- Algoritamska pristrasnost u UI: Ključni pojmovi, implikacije, i rješenja (Bosnian)
- Algoritamska pristranost u umjetnoj inteligenciji: Ključni pojmovi, implikacije i rješenja (Croatian)
- Algoritmická zaujatost v umělé inteligenci: Klíčové pojmy, dopady a řešení (Czech)

Additional materials needed

Projector; short case studies or news items about biased algorithms (search engines, recommendation systems, credit scoring, recruitment).

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Quick poll: “Where have you heard about AI being biased?” Collect examples and briefly classify them.

Core activity / exploration (45–60 minutes)

Students read the OER section defining algorithmic bias and its implications. In groups, they work on a case study (e.g., facial recognition, job ads, or library recommender systems), identifying:

- type of bias,
- affected groups (with focus on gender/intersectionality),
- underlying causes,
- potential remedies.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Each group produces a short “bias map” (diagram or table) and presents it. The teacher moderates a discussion linking the cases to professional codes of ethics in LIS.

Optional extension / homework

Students write a short policy brief or professional guideline for mitigating bias in a specific LIS context (e.g. library search, institutional repository).

Assessment and evaluation

Group “bias maps” can be evaluated on conceptual correctness and clarity; written policy briefs can be used for summative assessment.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Ethics of Information and AI; Data Governance; Information Retrieval; Digital Society.

Suggestions for adaptation

For less technical groups, focus more on impacts and less on model internals; for more technical groups, introduce simple fairness metrics or bias-detection tools.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.5 Teaching Prototype Package – Students’ Perception on Using ChatGPT for Educational Purposes and Gender Differences

Thematic focus

Students’ perceptions of generative AI (ChatGPT) in learning, with attention to gender differences in attitudes, practices and concerns.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Undergraduate and Master’s students in LIS, education, social sciences; also relevant for staff development workshops.

Approximate duration

60–90 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

None beyond basic familiarity with ChatGPT or similar tools.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, learners will be able to:

- Summarise key findings from the OER about students' use of ChatGPT.
- Discuss perceived benefits and risks of generative AI for learning.
- Reflect on possible gendered patterns in adoption, confidence and anxiety.
- Formulate guidelines for responsible, equitable use of ChatGPT in their context.

Core OER(s) included

- ❖ Percepcija studenata o korištenju ChatGPT-a za obrazovne svrhe i rodne razlike (Croatian)
- ❖ Percepcija studenata o korištenju ChatGPT-a u obrazovne svrhe i rodne razlike (Bosnian)
- ❖ Students' perception on using ChatGPT for educational purposes and gender differences (English)
- ❖ Precepción del estudiantado sobre el uso de ChatGPT con fines educativos y diferencias de género (Spanish)
- ❖ Precepció de l'estudiantat sobre l'ús de ChatGPT amb finalitats educatius i diferències de gènere (Catalan)
- ❖ Studierendenwahrnehmung der Nutzung von ChatGPT im Bildungsbereich und geschlechtsspezifische Unterschiede (German)
- ❖ Jak studenti vnímají používání ChatGPT v oblasti vzdělávání a rozdílů v pohlaví. (Czech)

Additional materials needed

Access to ChatGPT or similar tool (optional but helpful); whiteboard or shared document for collecting ideas.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

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Anonymous poll on students' own use of ChatGPT (frequency, purposes, confidence).
Quick comparison of results with the OER findings.

Core activity / exploration (30–40 minutes)

Groups read selected sections of the OER (methods, main results). Each group focuses on one dimension (e.g. perceived usefulness, fairness, anxiety, gender differences). They prepare a short summary including implications for teachers or librarians.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Group presentations followed by plenary discussion: what do these findings mean for course design, assessment policies and support services? The class drafts a short list of principles for fair and responsible use of ChatGPT.

Optional extension / homework

Students conduct a mini-survey in their own cohort and compare results to the OER case.

Assessment and evaluation

Participation in group work and quality of summaries; optional short reflection paper on how their own practices compare to those in the OER.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Educational Technology; Information Literacy; Research Methods in Education; Digital Scholarship.

Suggestions for adaptation

Can easily be used in staff workshops for discussing institutional policies; can be adapted to other tools beyond ChatGPT.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.6 Teaching Prototype Package – Gaming and Gender

Thematic focus

Representation, stereotypes and participation patterns in digital games, with a focus on gender and intersectionality.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Undergraduate students in LIS, media studies, game studies, education; suitable also for youth work or public library programmes.

Approximate duration

90 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

Familiarity with digital games as players or observers; basic awareness of gender stereotypes.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, learners will be able to:

- Identify common gender stereotypes in game narratives and character design.
- Discuss how game cultures may include or exclude different groups.
- Relate gaming practices to wider debates on gender, diversity and inclusion.
- Propose ways in which libraries and educators can use games critically and inclusively.

Core OER(s) included

- ❖ Gaming & Gender (English)
- ❖ Video-igre & spol (Bosnian)
- ❖ Videoigre i spol (Croatian)
- ❖ Videojuegos y Género (Spanish)
- ❖ Videojocs i gènere (Catalan)
- ❖ Videohry & Gender (Czech)
- Gaming und Gender (German)

Additional materials needed

Screenshots or short clips from selected games; access to a game platform is helpful but not essential.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Students anonymously list their favourite games and are invited to reflect on who the “typical player” is imagined to be.

Core activity / exploration (40–45 minutes)

Groups work with the OER to identify analytical dimensions (characters, narratives, mechanics, communities). Each group analyses one or two games (real or hypothetical) along these dimensions, focusing on gender and intersectionality.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Groups share their findings. The class discusses the potential of libraries and educators to use games while addressing stereotypes and inclusion.

Optional extension / homework

Students design a mini-exhibition or reading list in a library that connects games with gender-aware resources (books, comics, films).

Assessment and evaluation

Group analysis can be graded; optional short reflective essay on gaming experiences and gender can complement assessment.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Media and Youth; Popular Culture; Digital Literacies; Library Programming.

Suggestions for adaptation

For non-gaming students, the teacher can provide pre-selected titles; for online teaching, use pre-recorded gameplay.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.7 Teaching Prototype Package – Cultural Heritage and Gender

Thematic focus

Gendered dimensions of cultural heritage in GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, museums), including whose stories are preserved, highlighted or silenced.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Undergraduate and Master's students in LIS, archival studies, museology, cultural heritage; professionals in GLAM institutions.

Approximate duration

90–120 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

Basic understanding of cultural heritage institutions and their roles.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, learners will be able to:

- Describe how gender shapes the creation, preservation and display of heritage.
- Identify gaps and biases in collections or exhibitions from a gender perspective.
- Propose strategies for more inclusive, gender-aware heritage practices.
- Reflect on their future professional responsibilities in GLAM contexts.

Core OER(s) included

- ❖ Cultural Heritage and Gender (English)
- ❖ Patrimoni Cultural i Gènere (Catalan)
- ❖ Patrimonio Cultural y Género (Spanish)
- ❖ Kulturelles Erbe und Gender (German)
- ❖ Kulturno naslijeđe i rod (Bosnian)
- ❖ Kulturna baština i rod (Croatian)
- ❖ Kulturní dědictví a gender (Czech)

Additional materials needed

Examples from local collections (catalogue records, exhibition texts, digital collections) or case studies from the OER.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Students name a museum/library/archive they know and are asked: “Whose stories are most visible there?”

Core activity / exploration (45–60 minutes)

In groups, students read the OER and analyse a given case (collection, exhibition, digital gallery). They map:

- which groups are represented and how,
- which groups seem absent,
- what interpretative frameworks are used.

Groups then draft recommendations for making the case study more gender-inclusive.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Groups present their recommendations. Discussion focuses on feasibility and potential resistance.

Optional extension / homework

Students conduct a “gender walk” through a local heritage institution (physically or online) and document their observations with photos and notes.

Assessment and evaluation

Evaluation of group recommendations and participation; optional reflective journal entry on professional implications.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Cultural Heritage; Museum Studies; Archival Description; Collection Development.

Suggestions for adaptation

For online courses, use fully digital collections; for professional training, use real institutional data and invite staff to the final discussion.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.8 Teaching Prototype Package – Translation and Gender

Thematic focus

How translation practices shape and reflect gender, including inclusive language, pronouns, and representation across languages.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Students in LIS, translation studies, language and communication; also useful for librarians working with multilingual collections.

Approximate duration

60–90 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

Basic experience with translation or reading texts in more than one language.

Learning outcomes

- After completing this activity, learners will be able to:
- Identify gendered aspects of language and translation choices.
- Discuss how inclusive or non-inclusive language shapes perception.
- Experiment with different translation strategies to improve inclusivity.
- Reflect on ethical responsibilities when mediating texts across languages.

Core OER(s) included

- ❖ Translation and Gender (English)

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the European Union

- ❖ Traducción y género (Spanish)
- ❖ Traducció i gènere (Catalan)
- ❖ Übersetzung und Gender (German)
- ❖ Prevođenje i rod (Bosnian)
- ❖ Prevođenje i spol (Croatian)
- ❖ Překlad a gender (Czech)

Additional materials needed

Short extracts from policy documents, news items or library descriptions in one language; bilingual dictionaries or online tools.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Students share examples of gendered language in their own languages (job titles, generic masculine, etc.).

Core activity / exploration (30–40 minutes)

Groups read the OER segment on inclusive translation. Each group receives a short text in one language and is asked to translate it into another consortium language, making explicit decisions about gender-inclusive forms.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Groups compare their translations, discussing trade-offs, readability and alignment with institutional norms.

Optional extension / homework

Students revise existing institutional texts (e.g. library website) with gender-aware translation strategies.

Assessment and evaluation

Assessment can be based on translated texts and a brief commentary explaining choices; focus on reflection rather than “perfect” translation.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Translation Studies; Multilingual Information Services; Communication for LIS.

Suggestions for adaptation

Can be run monolingually by comparing “traditional” vs. gender-inclusive options; for online teaching, use shared documents for collaborative translation.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.9 Teaching Prototype Package – Hate Speech & Mis/Disinformation and the Status of Women in Socialist Contexts

Thematic focus

Hate speech and mis/disinformation, with a focus on representations and treatment of women in socialist and post-socialist contexts.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Students in LIS, political science, media studies, contemporary history; relevant for advanced undergraduate and Master’s levels.

Approximate duration

90–120 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

Basic understanding of disinformation and hate speech; some familiarity with European history is helpful.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, learners will be able to:

- Distinguish between hate speech, misinformation and disinformation.
- Analyse how women are represented in historical and contemporary narratives.
- Evaluate examples of media content from socialist or post-socialist contexts.
- Propose strategies for information professionals to address harmful narratives.

Core OER(s) included

- ❖ Hate Speech & Mis/Disinformation (English)
- ❖ Discurso de odio y desinformación (Spanish)
- ❖ Discurs d'odi i de desinformació (Catalan)
- ❖ Hassrede und Des-/Fehlinformation (German)
- ❖ Govor mržnje i mis/dezinformacije (Bosnian)
- ❖ Govor mržnje i mis/dezinformacije (Croatian)
- ❖ Nenávistné projevy a mis/dezinformace (Czech)

Additional materials needed

Short excerpts from historical newspapers, posters or contemporary online posts; guidelines on hate speech definitions.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Students discuss examples of hate speech or disinformation they have encountered and how they felt about them.

Core activity / exploration (45–60 minutes)

Using the OER, groups analyse curated examples (historical and recent). They identify:

- type of content (hate speech, mis/disinformation),
- explicit and implicit messages about women,
- historical or political context.

Groups then reflect on how such content circulates today (e.g. via social media, alternative media).

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Groups share insights on continuity and change in narratives about women. The plenary discussion addresses what libraries and archives can do to contextualise or counter these materials.

Optional extension / homework

Students design a small awareness campaign (poster or social media concept) based on the OER's key messages.

Assessment and evaluation

Assessment based on group analyses and campaign proposals; optional reflective note on emotional and ethical aspects of working with such content.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Media and Politics; History of Information; Information Ethics; Disinformation Studies.

Suggestions for adaptation

For more sensitive audiences, use only anonymised or less explicit content; for research-oriented groups, link the activity to corpus-based analysis.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.10 Teaching Prototype Package – Supporting Women in Intro CS/IT: First-Two-Weeks Faculty Playbook

Thematic focus

Intervention at the level of teaching practice to support women and gender-diverse students in introductory computer science and IT courses.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Teaching staff in CS/IT and related fields; also usable with LIS students preparing to teach or support digital skills.

Approximate duration

One 60–90 minute workshop (for staff) or integrated across several teaching sessions (for students).

Required prior knowledge

Experience in teaching or supporting teaching in technical subjects, or interest in pedagogical development.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, participants will be able to:

- Identify common barriers faced by women in intro CS/IT courses.
- Apply specific strategies from the playbook during the first two weeks of teaching.
- Reflect on their own teaching practices from a gender-aware perspective.

**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
Challenges in Higher Education**

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<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

- Plan small but concrete changes to their course design and classroom communication.

Core OER(s) included

- ❖ Supporting Women in Intro CS/IT (English)
- ❖ Apoyando a las mujeres en CS/IT (Spanish)
- ❖ Donant suport a les dones en CS/IT (Catalan)
- ❖ Frauen in Intro CS/IT unterstützen (German)
- ❖ Podrška ženama u uvodnom CS/IT (Bosnian)
- ❖ Podrška ženama u računalnim znanostima/IT (Croatian)
- ❖ Podpora žen v Intro CS/IT (Czech)

Additional materials needed

Copies of the playbook; example syllabi or course outlines; post-it notes or shared documents.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Participants share challenges they have observed among first-year CS/IT students, particularly women.

Core activity / exploration (40–50 minutes)

In small groups, participants work through sections of the playbook (e.g. classroom climate, early assessment, feedback). They annotate their own syllabi with concrete changes they could introduce in the first two weeks.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Groups present one or two planned changes and discuss potential obstacles (time, institutional culture).

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Optional extension / homework

Participants implement selected strategies and later report back (e.g. in a follow-up session or online forum).

Assessment and evaluation

This is primarily a developmental activity; feedback forms and short reflective notes can be used for evaluation.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Staff development programmes; Teaching and Learning in Higher Education; gender and STEM initiatives.

Suggestions for adaptation

Can be adapted to non-CS courses focusing on early-course climate and inclusion; can be integrated into longer training on gender and STEM.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.11 Teaching Prototype Package – Women in Science and Engineering in the EU

Thematic focus

Quantitative and visual analysis of the position of women in science and engineering across EU countries, using official Eurostat data and associated OER.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

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Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

Undergraduate and Master's students in LIS, data literacy, social statistics, gender studies; also useful for secondary-school outreach.

Approximate duration

90–120 minutes.

Required prior knowledge

Basic understanding of charts and percentages; introductory data literacy.

Learning outcomes

After completing this activity, learners will be able to:

- Interpret key indicators on women's participation in science and engineering.
- Compare countries or sectors and identify patterns in gender gaps.
- Critically discuss limitations of available statistics.
- Connect quantitative indicators to broader debates on gender equality in STEM.

Core OER(s) included

- ❖ Women in Science and Engineering in the EU (English)
- ❖ Mujeres en la ciencia e ingeniería en la UE (Spanish)
- ❖ Dones en la ciència i l'enginyeria a la UE (Catalan)
- ❖ Frauen in Wissenschaft und Technik in der EU (German)
- ❖ Žene u nauci i inženjerstvu u EU (Bosnian)
- ❖ Žene u znanosti i inženjerstvu u EU (Croatian)
- ❖ Ženy ve vědě a technice v EU (Czech)

Additional materials needed

Printouts or digital dashboards with the relevant graphs; simple spreadsheet or data tool (optional).

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Students guess approximate percentages of women in science and engineering in their country; then compare with OER data.

Core activity / exploration (45–60 minutes)

Groups work with the OER graphs and, optionally, underlying data. Each group focuses on a small set of countries or sectors and prepares a short analytical narrative: what patterns they see, where gaps are widest, how things change over time.

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Group presentations followed by discussion on possible explanations (education systems, policies, stereotypes) and implications for LIS professionals.

Optional extension / homework

Students produce a one-page infographic or short blog post summarising findings for a non-specialist audience.

Assessment and evaluation

Assessment based on analytical clarity and correct interpretation of data; optional evaluation of infographics or posts.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Data Literacy; Social Statistics; Gender and STEM; Evidence-Based Policy.

Suggestions for adaptation

Can be compressed into a short “data literacy” module; can be adapted for outreach events in schools or libraries.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

3.12 Teaching Prototype Package – Methodological Prototypes (Research & Evaluation)

Thematic focus

Research and evaluation methods for integrating gender perspectives into teaching and curricula: curriculum analysis, inclusive data collection, and the Delphi method.

Languages available

English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Bosnian, Croatian, Czech.

Target group

Master's students and doctoral candidates in LIS and education; teaching staff and librarians involved in research or curriculum development.

Approximate duration

Modular: 3 × 60–90 minutes (one per methodological OER) or a combined workshop.

Required prior knowledge

Basic understanding of research design and evaluation in social sciences or education.

Learning outcomes

After completing these activities, participants will be able to:

- Use a curriculum analysis rubric to identify where and how gender is integrated into teaching plans.
- Plan data collection with attention to inclusivity and representation in gender-focused research.

- Understand the logic and main steps of the Delphi method for building expert consensus.
- Apply these tools to design or evaluate gender-inclusive educational interventions.

Core OER(s) included

- ❖ Curriculum Analysis Rubric — Gender Perspectives in Teaching Plans
- ❖ What Data Are You Collecting? Inclusive Perspectives in Gender-Focused Research (and its multilingual versions)
- ❖ Delphi Method in Academic Research: A Step-by-Step Guide for Faculty Members (and its multilingual versions)

Additional materials needed

Sample syllabi or teaching plans; simple research scenarios; access to the full OER documents.

Suggested learning activities

Warm-up / activation (10–15 minutes)

Participants briefly share experiences of trying to “add gender” to courses or research projects.

Core activity / exploration (3 mini-blocks):

Curriculum analysis (30–40 minutes)

- Using the rubric OER, participants evaluate one of their own syllabi or a provided example.
- They identify strengths, gaps and possible improvements.

Inclusive data collection (30–40 minutes)

- Working with the “What Data Are You Collecting?” OER, participants review a sample questionnaire or interview guide and propose changes to better reflect gender diversity and intersectionality.

Delphi method (30–40 minutes)

- Participants read the Delphi OER and outline a small Delphi-based study (e.g. reaching consensus on priorities for gender-inclusive teaching in their institution).

Synthesis and reflection (20–25 minutes)

Discussion of how these tools can be combined in a local project (e.g. evaluating a programme, designing a new module).

Optional extension / homework

Participants develop a short methodological plan for a real mini-project (e.g. gender review of a degree programme).

Assessment and evaluation

Evaluation through methodological plans, revised syllabi, or redesigned instruments; reflection on challenges and feasibility.

Links to curricula and potential courses

Research Methods in LIS; Evaluation of Educational Programmes; Curriculum Design; Gender Studies.

Suggestions for adaptation

Can be implemented as a compact methods workshop or integrated piece by piece into longer research-methods courses.

Licence and citation

Recommended licence: CC BY.

4. Conclusions and future use

Finally, the reusable nature of the prototype teaching packages and the multilingual OER developed under WP2 strengthens the sustainability of the GEDIS results. It enables partners and external institutions to adapt and extend these materials beyond the lifetime of the project, while maintaining a strong focus on gender equality in information science education.

The educational frameworks and resources presented in this report will be reused and further validated in future project activities, including the Summer School in Opava (WP4), the workshop in Sarajevo (WP4) the workshop and online activities with Bosnian librarians, and the development of toolkits for students, professors and librarians (WP6). These activities will ensure continuity between the analysis, design and implementation phases, and will support the gradual mainstreaming of gender perspectives in teaching practice.

This report documents WP2 Result 3 by presenting a coherent set of prototype teaching packages built around multilingual OER. In doing so, it contributes directly to the WP2 objectives and provides a practical foundation for subsequent work on innovative, gender-responsive teaching in information science across the GEDIS consortium.